

vector

oe-circNRIP1

si-NC

si-circNRIP1

fig2D

fig2E

fig2F

fig2F

fig2F

fig2G

fig4G AGS

Vector	+	-	-	-
Oe-circNRIP1	-	+	+	+
Mimic NC	-	-	+	-
miR-148b-5p mimic	-	-	-	+

fig4G MKN-45

Si-NC +
si-circNRIP1 -
inhibitor NC -
miR-148b-5p inhibitor -

-

+

-

-

-

+

+

-

-

+

-

+

Vector +
Oe-circNRIP1 -
Mimic NC -
miR-148b-5p mimic -

-
+
-
-

-
+
+
-

-
+
-
+

fig4l AGS

Si-NC +
si-circNRIP1 -
inhibitor NC -
miR-148b-5p inhibitor -

-
+
-
-

-
+
+
-

-
+
-
+

fig4l
MKN-45

fig6l AGS

Inhibitor NC	+	-	-	-
Mir-148b-5p inhibitor	-	+	+	+
Si-NC	-	-	+	-
Si-CYR61	-	-	-	+

fig6I MKN-45

mimic NC	+	-	-	-
Mir-148b-5p mimic	-	+	+	+
pcDNA	-	-	+	-
pcDNA-CYR61	-	-	-	+

Fig 6K AGS

Inhibitor NC	+	-	-	-
Mir-148b-5p inhibitor	-	+	+	+
Si-NC	-	-	+	-
Si-CYR61	-	-	-	+

Fig 6K MKN-45

mimic NC	+	-	-	-
Mir-148b-5p mimic	-	+	+	+
pcDNA	-	-	+	-
pcDNA-CYR61	-	-	-	+

Fig 7A

Fig 7E

Fig 7E

sh-NC

sh-circNRIP1

CYR61

E-cadherin

Vimentin

Fig 7E

sh-NC

sh-circNRIP1

CYR61

E-cadherin

Vimentin

